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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DEE LAILA C. BUHIAN, DBA

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

laila.buhian@norsu.edu.ph

“A LIFE FULL OF STRUGLES AND STRENGTH”

I grew up in a loving and knowledgeable household.
with education given in a sacred setting.
My father, a leader who was both tough and kind,
My mother a teacher with nurturing heart.
Every one of my three brothers has their own preferences.
But the colors of life were gloomy and drab.

Lost in a realm so vast, the eldest among us,
For fifteen years, we were going to bear the suffering.
His brilliance faded as he lost his soul to drugs,
I was able to learn how to weather the storm, though.
It was his battle that cemented my heart.
Though I kept it to myself, I found a strength.

The second, fearless with an adventurous spirit,
pursuing wealth uncontrollably.
He spent and sold, then came back,
Not until his pockets were scorched.
And before father leave from this world,
He made a vow to be good.

The youngest, dependable, good, and wise,
With healing hands and a growing heart.
Now a surgeon with a clear objective,
A guiding light, a powerful beacon.
He remained steadfast,
An epitome of strength I truly admired.

However, childhood wasn't always kind.
with severe wounds that have been left behind.
I carried the burden of humiliation and anguish.
However, I embraced the blaze and stood my stand.

For even grief, suffering, and conflict,
could never, ever weaken my will.

Despite the difficulties I've faced in my past,
I stood still and kept my strong spirit.
I stepped out from the shadows and took charge my own destiny
stepping into better times and out of the shadows.
I am no longer constrained by the chapters I have left behind; I am free now.
With dreams yet to come true, with loss and love forming my identity.

